

ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;ksa ls pkoy dh mRikndrk esa lqèkkj

MkW- iwtk xqlrk

tyok;q ifjorZu ds udkjkRed çHkkoksa vkSj oSfÜod vkcknh dh Rofjr o`f) dks ns[krs gq,] ty lalkèkuksa ds laj{k.k] pkoy dh mRikndrk esa lqèkkj vkSj lexz dq'ky pkoy dh [ksrh dks c<+kok nsus ds fy, IVhd flapkbZ egRoiw.kZ gS] D;ksafd pkoy vU; Qlyksa dh rgyuk esa vfèkd ikuh dh [kir djus okyh Qly gSA - dbZ n'kdksa ls] ty mi;ksx n{krk $\frac{1}{4}$ MCY;w;wbZ $\frac{1}{2}$ dks mYys[kuh; :i ls c<+kus ds fy, fofHkUu ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;ksa dk vè;;u fd;k x;k gSA bl isij dk mís'; flafpr ç.kkfy;ksa ds çn'kZu ladsrdksa dks Li"V djus ds ckn] flafpr pkoy mRiknu esa ikuh dh cpr esa ;ksxnku djus ds fy, pkoy dh Qly dh ikuh dh vko';drkvksa dk vkdyu djus ds fy, eq[; çkS|ksfxfd;ksa vkSj –f"Vdks.kksa dh leh{kk djuk gSA fiNys vè;;uksa ds dbZ oSKkfud ys[kksa dk ijke'kZ vkSj fo'ys"k.k fd;k x;kA bu vè;;uksa ls irk pyk gS fd flapkbZ ty laj{k.k esa Qly flapkbZ ty vko';drkvksa ds vkdyu ls ysdj [ksr esa ikuh cpkus dh çFkkvksa ds dk;kZUo;u rd dbZ çdkj dh çFkk,a 'kkfey gSaA blds vykok] flapkbZ ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;ksa dks rhu lewgksa esa oxÊ—r fd;k tk ldrk gS] vFkkZr~ ty&laj{k.k flapkbZ ç.kkfy;kj] ty&cpr flapkbZ fofèk;kj] vkSj ty&laj{k.k —f"k i)fr;kjA O;fäxr vkSj la;qä flapkbZ ty mi;ksx n{krk midj.kksa ds çHkko ij çdk'k Mkyk x;kA ;g isij 'kksèkdrkZvksa dks pkoy dh Qly esa ikuh dh vko';drkvksa dk vuqeku yxkus ds fy, ty&cpr ds rjhdksa ij Kku çklr djus esa l{ke

djsxk vkSj bl çdkj mUgsa fofHkUu ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;ksa dk mi;ksx djds flafpr pkoy dh [ksrh ç.kkfy;ksa ds çn'kZu dks csgrj cukus esa çHkkoh <ax ls ;ksxnku djus dh vuqefr nsxkA

[kkst'kCn: ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;k;(flapkbZ(ty mRikndrk(ty mi;ksx n{krk(pkoy mRiknu

pkoy dks nqfu;k esa lcls vfèkd [kk;k tkus okyk Hkkstu ekuk tkrk gS] vkSj blfy, [kk| vlqj{kk ds f[kykQ yM+kbZ esa ;g vifjgk;Z gS] [kkldj detksj vFkZO;oLFkk okys ns'kksa esa A eksfgnse ,V vy ds vuqlkjA] nqfu;k dh vkèkh ls vfèkd vkcknh [kk| lqj{kk ds fy, pkoy ij fuHkZj gSA bl çdkj] bu ns'kksa esa c<+rh vkcknh vkSj [kku&iku dh vknrksa esa cnyko dks ns[krs gq, pkoy dh yxkrkj c<+rh ekax dks iwjk djus ds fy, pkoy mRiknu esa lqèkkj fd;k tkuk pkfg,A 2030 rd] oSfÜod pkoy mRiknu 58 ls c<+dj 567 fefy;u Vu gksus dh mEehn gS A blds vykok] mPp mRikndrk] Qly l?kurk vkSj fofòèkhdj.k ds ekè;e ls 2050 rd nqfu;k dk pkoy mRiknu 1035 fefy;u Vu ls vfèkd c<+us dk vuqeku gSA- blds vykok] pkoy ,d tyh; ;k vèkZ&tyh; Qly gS] vkSj blfy, rkts ikuh ds mi;ksx ds ekeys esa bldh lcls vfèkd ekax gSA fcu jgeku vkSj >kax ds vuqlkj] ,f'k;k esa lHkh flafpr rkts ikuh ds lalkèkuksa esa pkoy dh [kir 80% ls vfèkd gS] blfy,] ikuh dh cpr djrs gq, vukt mRikndrk dks c<+kuk pkoy dh [ksrh ds fy, ,d cM+h pqukSrh gSA nqHkkZX; ls] —f"k mRiknu ds fy, vko';d çk— frd lalkèku] vFkkZr~ ikuh vkSj Hkwfe@feêh] vewrZ gSa vkSj blfy, leklr gksus ;ksX; gSa] [kkldj tc tyok;q ifjorZu vkSj tula[;k o`f) ds

udkjRed çHkkoksa ds dkj.k mudk çcaèku [kjkç gksrk gS- blfy,] pkoy dh [ksrh orZeku esa dqN leL;kvksa dk lkeuk dj jgh gS] tSlS ikuh dh deh] ikuh vkSj feêh dh xq.koÙkk esa fxjkoV] feêh dh moZjrk esa fxjkoV vkfnA A 5&10 lseh ikuh dh xgjkBZ ds lkFk ck<+ flapkbZ] pkoy mRiknu ds fy, nqfu;k Hkj esa O;kid :i ls çpfyr gS] vkSj fujarj ck<+ lalkèkuksa dh deh vkSj pkoy flapkbZ ;kstukvksa ds rgr ntZ fd, x, çn'kZu esa deh ds fy, ftEesnkj çeq[k dkjd gSa A

pkoy dh [ksrh ds i;kZoj.kh; çHkko dks de djus vkSj LekVZ vkSj fVdkÅ pkoy mRiknu dks c<+kok nsus ds fy, dbZ vè;;u fd, x, gSa] tSlS xzhugkml xSl mRitZu dks de djuk] pkoy dh [ksrh ds fy, mi;ksx fd, tkus okys ikuh vkSj moZjdxsa dk vuqdwyu] vkSj èkku dh iSnkokj vkSj feYM pkoy dh xq.koÙkk esa lqèkkj djukA bl çdkj] pkoy dh [ksrh ds fy, dbZ ty vkSj feêh laj{k.k çFkkvksa dks fodflr fd;k x;k vkSj ikuh vkSj feêh çcaèku esa lqèkkj ds lkFk&lkFk dq'ky flapkbZ ç.kkyh fodflr djus ds fy, pkoy dh [ksrh ij ykxw fd;k x;kA bu çS|ksfxd;ksa dh çHkko'khyrk dk ewY;kadu ty çcaèku ladsrdksa] tSlS ty mi;ksx n{krk@ty mRikndrk] dk mi;ksx djds fd;k tkrk gSA gkyk;fd] bu çn'kZu ladsrdksa dk vFkZ vkSj dHkh&dHkh vuqeku yxkus dk rjhdk ,d ys[kd ls nwljs ys[kd esa fHkUu gksrk gSA ;g leh{k flafpr pkoy dh [ksrh ds rgr fofHkUu ty çcaèku çFkkvksa vkSj —f" k ty mRikndrk vkSj çk—frd lalkèkuksa ¼;kuh] feêh vkSj ikuh½ laj{k.k ij muds çHkko ij dsafær gSA ;g 'kksèkdrkZvksa dks —f" k ty çcaèku ¼MCY;w;wbZ] MCY;wih vkSj MCY;w,lbZ½ ls lacafèkr eq[;

voèkkj.kkvksa dks vyx djus vkSj pkoy dh Qly dh ikuh dh vko';drkvksa dk vkdyu djus ds rjhdksa] mi;qä flapkbZ ç.kkfy;ksa lfgr pkoy dh [ksrh esa ikuh dh cpr ds fofHkUu rjhdksa dks le>us esa l{ke djsxkA] vPNh flapkbZ i)fr;kj vkSj vPNh —f" k i)fr;kjA

ty çcaèku voèkkj.kk,i

ty mRikndrk $\frac{1}{4}$ MCY;wih $\frac{1}{2}$ @ty mi;ksx n{krk $\frac{1}{4}$ MCY;w;wbZ $\frac{1}{2}$

flapkbZ çn'kZu ladsrd] tSls WP@WUE] dk mi;ksx ty laj{k.k lqfuf'pr djus ds fy, fd;k tkrk gS vkSj blfy, LFkk;h —f" k ty çcaèku dk leFkZu fd;k tkrk gS A bl çdkj] ty mRikndrk vkSj ty mi;ksx n{krk esa o`f) ty lalkèkuksa ds laj{k.k] ikuh dh deh dks de djus vkSj fVdkÅ — f" k çklr djus ds fy, ,d 'krZ gS A nqHkkZX; ls] gky ds dbZ vè;;uksa esa nksuksa 'kCnksa dk mi;ksx fcuk fdlh Hksn ds fd;k x;k gS A fdyseks vkSj jxkc us nkok fd;k fd ty mi;ksx n{krk vkSj ty mRikndrk nks vyx voèkkj.kk,i gSa ysfdu 'kksèk esa vfrO;kih 'kCn gSaA blds vfrfjä] flapkbZ ty çcaèku esa ikuh ds mi;ksx ds fofHkUu iSekuksa vkSj Mkkesu ds fy, bu voèkkj.kkvksa dh ifjHkk"kkvksa vkSj vuqç;ksxksa dk nq#i;ksx fd;k tkrk gS A

blds vykok] ty mRikndrk $\frac{1}{4}$ MCY;wih $\frac{1}{2}$ 'kCn dk mi;ksx mRiknu ;k vk; $\frac{1}{4}$ tSls ck;ksekl ;k mit $\frac{1}{2}$ vkSj ty lalkèku dh ek=k ds chp lacaèk dks vfèkd IVhd :i ls fpf=r djus ds fy, fd;k tkrk gS] tcfD MCY;w;wbZ ikuh dh [kir ds fy, çHkkoh ty ekax ds vuqikr ;k çfr'kr dks ekirk gSA A dEcksm ,V vy ds vuqlkjA]vfèkdka'k ifjHkk"kk,i

WUE dks flapkbZ n{krk ds eki ds :i esa ekurh gSa] vkSj WP dks Qlyksa }kjk okLrfod ikuh dh [kir ls lacafèkr ck;ksekl mRiknu vkSj Qly mit fuekZ.k dh 'kkjhfd çfØ;kvksa dh n{krk ds eki ds :i esa ekurh gSaA blds vykok] gSeMh vkSj jxkc ds vuqlkj] n{krk ,d çfr'kr gS vkSj bls vkmViqV vkSj buiqV ds vuqikr ds :i esa ifjHkkf"kr fd;k x;k gSA blfy,] flapkbZ n{krk Qlyksa }kjk mudh o`f) vofèk ds nkSjku fn, x, flapkbZ ty ¼ikSèkksa dh o`f) ds fy, mi;ksx fd, x, ikuh dh ek=k½ vkSj mlh vofèk ds nkSjku ykxw fd, x, ikuh ¼vkiwfrZ fd, x, ikuh dh ek=k½ dk vuqikr gSA tSlk fd gfl;kvks vkSj vU; us nkok fd;k gS] fdlh Hkh mRiknu çfØ;k dh n{krk ¼bZ½ vke rkSj ij vkSj vDlj vFkZ'kkL= esa ml çfØ;k ds fy, vkmViqV vkSj buiqV ds vuqikr ds :i esa mi;ksx dh tkrh gS] nksuksa dks ek=kRed bdkb;ksa esa ekik tkrk gSA blds vykok] >kax ,V vyA vuqeku yxk,a fd WUE dk eku tks 'kwU; ls ,d rd fHkUu gksrk gS] mldh dksbZ bdkbZ ugha gksrh ¼;kuh] lkis{k eku½ vkSj ;g lcls çHkkoh gksrk gS tc bldk eku 1 ds cjkj gksrk gSA

fdyseks ds vuqlkj] "ty mi;ksx n{krk" 'kCn dh "vkd"kZdrk" dbZ oSKkfudksa dks mu fLFkfr;ksa esa Hkh bldk mi;ksx djus ds fy, çksRlkfgr djrh gS tgka ;g ykxw ugha gksrk gS] ftlds dkj.k bldk xyr mi;ksx gqv k gSA WUE ty buiqV ds vuqikr ;k çfr'kr dks ekirk gS tks —f" k ç.kkyh esa bfPNr Qlyksa rd igqapr k gS vkSj vo'kksf"kr gksrk gSA >kax ,V vy ds vuqlkj-] 'kCn "—f" k ty mi;ksx n{krk" ¼AWUE½ mu Qlyksa dh ek=k dks lanfHkZr djrk gS tks flapkbZ ty vkSj o"kkZ

lfgr ty lalkèkuksa dh çfr bdkbZ mRikfnr dh tk ldrh gSaA bu nks ifjHkk"kkvksa ls] ;g ns[kk tk ldrk gS fd ty mi;ksx n{krk Qly }kjk bls mRiknu ds fy, mi;ksx fd, tkus okys flapkbZ ty vkSj o"kkZ ty dks è;ku esa j[krh gS vkSj bls fdxz@,e3 esa O;ä fd;k tkrk gSA vU; ys[kdksa us WUE dh ifjHkk"kk esa rdudh] lkekftd&vkfFkZd vkSj i;kZoj.kh; dkjdxsa dks tksM+k gSA njvly] —f"k ty mi;ksx n{krk $\frac{1}{4}MCY;w;wbZ\frac{1}{2}$] tSlk fd fy;w ,V vy }kjk ifjHkkf"kr fd;k x;k gSA] ty lalkèkuksa ds fy, buiqV vkSj vkmViqV ds chp dk lacaèk gS tks ikuh dh ,d bdkbZ ds mi;ksx ls gksus okys vkfFkZd vkSj lkekftd ykHkksa dk o.kZu djrk gSA

dqN ys[kdksa us uhps mfYyf[kr lehdj.kksa dk mi;ksx djds ty mRikndrk $\frac{1}{4}MCY;wih\frac{1}{2}$] flapkbZ ty mRikndrk $\frac{1}{4}vkbZMCY;wih\frac{1}{2}$] ty miHkksx mRikndrk $\frac{1}{4}MCY;wlh\frac{1}{2}$] ty mi;ksx n{krk $\frac{1}{4}MCY;w;wbZ\frac{1}{2}$ vkSj flapkbZ ty mi;ksx n{krk $\frac{1}{4}vkbZMCY;w;wbZ\frac{1}{2}$ dh x.kuk dh:

$\frac{1}{4}1\frac{1}{2} WP \frac{3}{4}$ vukt mit flapkbZ \$ o"kkZ $WP \frac{3}{4}$ vukt mit flapkbZ \$ o"kkZ

WP= Grain yield Irrigation + Rainfall WP= Grain yield Irrigation + Rainfall

$\frac{1}{4}2\frac{1}{2}$

$WCP\frac{3}{4}$ vukt mit $kc \times ET_0$ $WCP \frac{3}{4}$ vukt mit $kc \times ET_0$

WCP =Grain yield $kc \times ET_0$ WCP = Grain yield $kc \times ET_0$

flapkbZ ty dh ekax vkSj pkoy dh Qly dh ty vko';drk,i

flapkbZ ty ekax dh [kjk le> ds dkj.k ty&cpr flapkbZ çkS|ksfxd;ksa dks c<+kok nsus ds ckotwn flapkbZ ty ekax

$\frac{1}{4}vkbZMCY;wMh\frac{1}{2}$ dh ek=k vHkh Hkh vfèkd gSA mnkgj.k ds fy,] gqISu ,V vyA ckaXykns'k esa ik;k x;k fd pkoy dh Qly ds fy, flapkbZ ty dh vko';drk 358 feeh ls 445 feeh rd gSA phu esa] pkoy ds fy, flapkbZ dk ikuh 135 feeh ls 288 feeh rd Fkka mÙkjH csfuu esa pkoy dh Qly ds fy, flapkbZ ds ikuh dh vko';drkvksa dk vuqeku ckSjSek ,V vy }kjk yxk;k x;k Fkka cjlkr ds ekSle esa 383 feeh vkSj 'kq"d ekSle esa 1148 feeh gksuk pkfg,A Mh ozhl ,V vy ds vuqlkjA lgsfy;u {ks=ksa esa pkoy dh Qly ds fy, flapkbZ dk ikuh 480 feeh ls 1490 feeh rd Fkka

pkoy flapkbZ ty ekax $\frac{1}{4}vkbZMCY;wMh\frac{1}{2}$ dks vçrfcafèkr feêh dh ifjLFkfr;ksa esa mxus okyh jksx&eqä Qly vkSj iw.kZ mRiknu çklr djus ds fy, vko';d ikuh dh ek=k ds :i esa ifjHkkf"kr fd;k x;k gSA nwljh vksj] Qly ty vko';drk,a $\frac{1}{4}lhMCY;wvkj\frac{1}{2}$;k Qly ok"ihdj.k $\frac{1}{4}bZVhlh\frac{1}{2}$ dk çrfufèkRo djus okyh Qly }kjk [kir fd;k tkus okyk ikuh Qly flapkbZ ty ekax ls fHkUu gksrk gS] tks vkerkSj ij vR;fèkd o"kkZ okys {ks=ksa esa cjlkr ds ekSle ds nkSjku de ;k vfLrRoghu gksrk gSA eq[; :i ls Qly dkjdxsa $\frac{1}{4}mnkgj.k$ ds fy,] fodkl pj.k] fdLesa] Qly 'kjhj fØ;k foKku] vkfn $\frac{1}{2}$ vkSj lanHkZ ok"ihdj.k $\frac{1}{4}bZVhvks\frac{1}{2}$ ls çHkkfor gksrk gS] tcfD mijksä dkjdxsa ds vykok] flapkbZ ty dh ekax] flapkbZ çcaèku çFkkvksa $\frac{1}{4}mnkgj.k$ ds fy,] flapkbZ fofèk;ksa $\frac{1}{2}$ ls çHkkfor gksrh gSA flapkbZ O;oLFkk] flapkbZ 'ksMîwfyax] flapkbZ çkS[ksfxfd;kj] vkfn $\frac{1}{2}$] —f"k lacaèkh çFkk,j $\frac{1}{4}tSls]$ Hkwfe dh rS;kjh] flapkbZ ;kstuk iSVuZ] vkfn $\frac{1}{2}$] feêh

dk çdkj ¼tSls] cukoV] <yku] gkbM^aksfyd] vkfn½] ekSle ¼tSls] o"kkZ½] vkSj fdlkuksa dk Kku@dkS'kyA bl çdkj] flapkbZ ty&cpr çcaèku çFkkvksa dks viukus vkSj lokZsÙke çcaèku çFkkvksa ij mRikndksa dh {kerk fuekZ.k ds ekè;e ls bls çHkkfor djus okys dkjdxsa ij dk;Z djds flapkbZ ty dh ekax dks de fd;k tk ldrk gSA

pkoy mRiknu ds fy, ty&cpr rduhdsa

pkoy dh [ksrh ds fy, ty&cpr çkS|ksfxd;k; fofòk gSa vkSj bUgsa rhu lewgksa esa oxÊ—r fd;k tk ldrk gS: ty&cpr flapkbZ ç.kkyh(ty&cpr flapkbZ i)fr;k; vkSj ty&cpr —f"k i)fr;k;A

pkoy mRiknu ds fy, ty&cpr flapkbZ ç.kkyh

pkoy mRiknu ds fy, vkerkSj ij lrg flapkbZ fofèk;ksa dk mi;ksx fd;k tkrk gSA gkyk;fd] ,jksfd ifjLFkfr;ksa esa pkoy dk mRiknu djus dh ykxr vkSj ykHk ck<+ dk ,d fodYi gS] tks [kjirokj vkSj vU; dhVksa dks de djus ds fy, ,d dq'ky rduhd gS ysfdu blesa cgqr vfèkd ikuh dk mi;ksx gksrk gSA dbZ ys[kdksa ds vuq[kj] vfèkdka'k Hkwfe dh flapkbZ lrg rjhdksa ls dh tkrh gS ftlesa ikuh dks Hkwfe çokg ds ekè;e ls iwjs [ksr esa forfjr fd;k tkrk gSA gkyk;fd] ikuh vkSj moZjd mi;ksx n{krk esa lqèkkj ds fy, pkoy dh Qly dks fM^ai ;k fLçadyj flapkbZ ç.kkyh ds rgr Hkh mxk;k tk ldrk gS] D;ksafd ck<+ vH;kl esa —f"k esa fdlh Hkh vU; Qly dh rgyuk esa pkoy ds mRiknu ds fy, vfèkd ty infpà 'kkfey gksrk gSA

pkoy mRiknu ds fy, lrgH flapkbZ fofèk;kj

mudh de n{krk vkSj ,d:irk ds ckotwn] vU; flapkbZ fofèk;ksa esa [kjkç fMtkbu vkSj ty çcaèku ds dkj.k] lrgH flapkbZ fofèk;ksa dk nqfu;k esa lcls vfèkd mi;ksx fd;k tkrk gSA csflu flapkbZ] lhek flapkbZ vkSj Q+jks flapkbZ lfgl lrgH flapkbZ fofèk;ksa dh fo'ks"krk vdq'ky flapkbZ gS] ftlls ikuh dh cckZnh] ty teko] yo.khdj.k vkSj lrgH vkSj Hkwty lalkèkuksa dk çnw"k.k gksrk gSA xq#Rokd"kZ.k vkèkkfjr flafpr ;kstukvksa ij pkoy dh [ksrh dks fVdkÅ cukus ds fy,] dbZ vè;;uksa us u dsoy ty&cpr çFkkvksa ij è;ku dsafær fd;k] cfYd Q+jks flapkbZ ij Hkh è;ku dsafær fd;kA

gkMZds vkSj DySisdK us fn[kk;k fd vklku Qly pØ vkSj ck<+ flafpr pkoy mRiknu dh rgyuk esa le; vkSj ykxR esa deh ds dkj.k vesfjdk esa gky ds o"kksZa esa Q+jks flafpr pkoy dk mRiknu c<+ jgk gS] tks 2015 esa 1% ls de gksdj 2019 esa 10% gks x;k gSA LVhoal ,V vy ds vuqlkj- de ikuh vkSj Je ds lkFk pkoy mxkus ds fy, Q+jks flapkbZ fofèk ikjaifjd ck<+ flapkbZ ls csgrj gS vkSj ;g flafpr pkoy ds vukt esa vklZsfud lkexzh dks de djus esa ;ksxnku nsrh gSA vU; vè;;uksa ls irk pyk gS fd Q+jks flafpr pkoy ds fy, mit ?kVd vkSj pkoy dh mit de Fkh tcfd ck<+ flapkbZ ds fy, pkoy esa vklZsfud dh ek=k vfèkd gksrh gSA

dbZ ys[kdkksa us fn[kk;k gS fd ikjaifjd flapkbZ dh rgyuk esa dqam flapkbZ ç.kkyh ds dbZ Qk;ns gSa:

- ;g fjlk] ok"ihdj.k vkSj ok"ihdj.k&mRltZu ds ekè;e ls flapkbZ ty gkfu nj dks dkQh de dj ldrk gS(
- ;g Qsjl vk;u tSlh gkfudkj d lkefxz;ksa dks de dj ldrk gS(
- ;g pkoy ds [ksr dh ueh dks de dj ldrk gS vkSj feêh esa xSl ifjogu vkSj çdk'k ços'k dks c<+k ldrk gS(
- ;g pkoy dh chekfj;ksa dks de dj ldrk gS vkSj ifj.kkeLo:i iÙkh dh thou 'kfä c<+k ldrk gS(vkSj
- ;g vukt dh iSnkokj vkSj ty mRikndrk c<+k ldrk gSA

fu"d"kZ

flapkbZ ty dh [kir dh çHkko'khyrk c<+kus ds fy,] bl leh{kk esa flafpr pkoy mRiknu esa mi;ksx dh tkus okyh dbZ ty laj{k.k rduhdksa dh tkap dh xbZA lcls igys] bl leh{kk us flapkbZ ty çcaèku dh dqN voèkkj.kkvksa dks Li"V fd;k] tSlS ty mRikndrk $\frac{1}{4}MCY;wih\frac{1}{2}$] ty mi;ksx n{krk $\frac{1}{4}MCY;w;wbZ\frac{1}{2}$ vkSj ty cpr n{krk $\frac{1}{4}MCY;w;lbZ\frac{1}{2}A$ Li"Vhdj.k çnku fd;k x;k D;ksafd lkfgR; esa dbZ 'kksèkdrkZvksa }kjk bu voèkkj.kkvksa dk mi;ksx vDlj Hkzfer djus okyk gksrk gSA nwljs] bl vè;;u esa flafpr pkoy mRiknu esa flapkbZ ty dh vko';drkvksa dk vuqeku yxkus ds fy, mi;ksx dh tkus okyh fofHkUu fofèk;ksa dh leh{kk dh xbZ] D;ksafd dqN fofèk;kj nwljksa dh rgyuk esa ty laj{k.k esa vfèkd ;ksxnku nsrh gSaA rhljs] pkoy mRiknu esa ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxd;ksa dh leh{kk dh xbZA

bl leh{k k esa ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;ksa dh rhu Jsf.k;ksa dks çfrf"Br fd;k x;k: ty&cpr flapkbZ ç.kkfy;kj] ty&cpr flapkbZ fofèk;kj vkSj ty&cpr —f" k i)fr;kjA Q+jks flapkbZ] fM^ai flapkbZ vkSj fLçadyj flapkbZ lfgr ty&cpr flapkbZ ç.kkfy;kj] pkoy dh [ksrh esa ty lalkèkuksa dk laj{k.k djrh gSaA ikuh dh cpr djus okyh flapkbZ fofèk;kj ftuesa AWD] M^akbZ lhfMax vkfn 'kkfey gSa] [ksr esa ikuh yxkus dh dqN vU; çFkk,; gSa tks flapkbZ ds ikuh dks cpkrh gSaA blh rjg] ty&cpr djus okyh —f" k i)fr;kj] tSlS efYpax] U;wure tqrkBZ] dkcZfud inkFkZ dk mi;ksx vkfn Hkh pkoy dh [ksrh esa ikuh ds mi;ksx esa lqèkkj djrh gSaA var esa] bl vè;;u us pkoy dh iSnkokj vkSj ty mi;ksx n{krk ij ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;ksa ds çHkko dk fo'ys" k.k fd;kA ;g ik;k x;k fd] ikjaifjd rjhdksa dh rkyuk esa] ty laj{k.k çkS|ksfxfd;ksa ls ty mi;ksx n{krk esa cgqr lqèkkj gksrk gSA gkyk;fd] ikjaifjd rjhdksa dh rkyuk esa pkoy dh iSnkokj esa lqèkkj esa mudk ;ksxnku fefJr jgrk gSA

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